

First records of *Phylloscopus collybita brevirostris* (Strickland, 1837) and *Ph. c. caucasicus* (Loskot, 1991) in north-western Europe

Peter de Knijff & Marije te Raa.

Department of Human Genetics, Leiden University Medical Center, Leiden, The Netherlands.

This document with public access URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13378568> was prepared as supplementary information to the following article submitted to The Bulletin of the British Ornithologists' Club: *First records of two Common Chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita* (Vieillot, 1817) taxa from the Middle East and the Caucasus in north-western Europe*

by Vincent van der Spek, Jochen Dierschke, José Luis Copete & Peter de Knijff

Summary

Six subspecies of the Common Chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita* are usually recognised, of which three are known to occur in North-western Europe: *collybita*, *abietinus*, and *tristis*. Based on DNA sequences, the taxa *brevirostris* and *caucasicus* are recorded from North-western Europe for the first time. Both taxa occur at the south-eastern edges of the species' breeding range, in the Middle East and the Caucasus, respectively. Movements outside the breeding season of these two taxa have been largely undescribed. A single *brevirostris* in Germany concerned a spring record, whereas five *caucasicus* in the Netherlands and Germany were recorded during late autumn. Based on published information, neither the genetic variation in the mitochondrial (mtDNA) ND2 gene (Raković et al. 2019), nor in the mtDNA CYTB gene (Helbig et al. 1996, Marova et al. 2021) enabled a reliable differentiation of *brevirostris* from *caucasicus*. Here we describe in some detail how the additional mtDNA-fragments do facilitate the identification of *brevirostris* and *caucasicus* unequivocally.

Laboratory procedures

All laboratory procedures described in this document have been described in detail by de Knijff (2024) and will not be repeated here. Based on the full mtDNA sequences (de Knijff et al., manuscript in preparation) of multiple individuals of all 12 taxa of the Common Chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita* complex, we became aware of the fact that, in contrast to previously published information (Helbig et al. 1996, Marova et al. 2021, Raković et al. 2019), the two genetically very similar taxa *Ph. c. brevirostris* and *Ph. c. caucasicus* can be reliably distinguished from each other by polymorphisms in three short mtDNA fragments in addition to CYTB and/or ND2.

Samples

Upon observing that neither the full ND2 gene nor the full cytb gene enabled a reliable differentiation between *brevirostris* and *caucasicus* and only identified these two taxa as a single group, we first explored which short mtDNA fragments on their own or in combination with ND2 and/or CYTB would allow *brevirostris* and *caucasicus* to be distinguished from each other. As a result, we identified three short fragments, ND1 (110 bp.), ATP8/ATP6 (240 bp.), and ND3/tRNA-ARG (125 bp.) that could function as good candidates. We designed PCR-primers and sequence protocols for these three fragments (see de Knijff, 2024) and sequenced these three fragments, as well as the full ND2 gene (1040 bp.) and a large fragment of the cytb gene (945 bp.) in a small panel (n=19) of relevant reference individuals (see Table 1) to further explore their use in various combinations (see below for results). Subsequently, these three additional fragments were sequenced in all potential *brevirostris/caucasicus* individuals identified in our large screening project of over 1200 samples. At the end of this document, we present a concatenated sequence file (fasta-format) of all five fragments in all reference samples.

Table 1. Reference sample information

Sample code	Taxon	Origin	Date	Sample code	Taxon	Origin	Date
TT0095	ABIE	Zweden	11-jun-98	TT0043	CAUC	Georgië	
TT0096	ABIE	Zweden	12-jun-98	TT0685	CAUC	Iran	14-jun-78
TT0049	COLY	Zweden	12-jul-11	TT0686	CAUC	Azerbaidjan	25-mei-81
TT0116	COLY	Nederland	24-aug-12	TT0056	MENZ	Georgië	
TT0280	BRE1	Turkije	13-mei-08	TT0057	MENZ	Georgië	
TT0070	BRE1	Turkije	14-jun-10	TT0798	MENZ	Iran	21-jul-35
TT0075	BRE1	Turkije	14-jun-10	TT1113	HERM	Israel	5-jun-20
TT0073	BRE2	Turkije	14-jun-10	TT1114	HERM	Israel	5-jun-20
TT0274	BRE2	Turkije	11-mei-08	TT1117	HERM	Israel	12-jul-19
TT0279	BRE2	Turkije	11-mei-08				

Network preparation and analyses

The various combinations of mtDNA gene fragments were aligned using BioEdit 7.2.5 (Hall 1999). As a second step, we used DnaSP v6 (from <http://www.ub.edu/dnasp/>), to extract and export a polymorphic-sites-only file in RDF-format from this fasta file. The resulting *.rdf file was used to prepare a median joining network using Network 10.2 (from <https://www.fluxus-engineering.com/sharenet.htm>). The network was adjusted using Network Publisher (purchased via <https://www.fluxus-engineering.com/sharenet.htm>), and subsequently exported as an *.emf file. This *.emf file was ungrouped and further edited and polished in PowerPoint which resulted in the network figures in this document.

Results

We first analysed the sequence variation of ND2 and CYTB among the reference samples of each gene separately in order to verify the previous observations that *brevirostris* and *caucasicus* could not be distinguished using either of these two mtDNA genes (Helbig et al. 1996, Marova et al. 2021, Raković et al. 2019). The resulting Median Joining networks of each of these two genes are shown in Figures 1 and 2 below.

As can be seen in both figures, on their own ND2 and CYTB indeed do not differentiate between *brevirostris* and *caucasicus*, especially not without prior knowledge, as was already previously concluded by others. What is also clear is that the networks of both mtDNA genes reveal subtly different genetic affinities among the 6 different taxa. This should be seen as a caution against concluding too much based on using single mtDNA genes as, apparently, the choice of the gene will influence the outcome

Figure 1. Network of variation in the mtDNA ND2 gene (1040 bp.) of six Common chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita sensu lato* taxa. For this network, sequences of 19 individuals (see Table 1) were used. Each circle represents unique ND2 sequence (haplotype) of 1040 bp. The relative diameter of each circle is an indication of its frequency in total dataset (n=19). Numbers inside circles: number of times that a haplotype was observed. Circles without number: haplotypes that were found in one individual only. Small black dots: inferred (not observed) haplotypes necessary to construct the network. Short lines between circles without a number mark differences between two haplotypes on one position (out of 1040 bp.), other longer lines mark two or more (as indicated by numbers along lines) different positions.

Figure 2. Network of variation in the mtDNA CYTB gene fragment (945 bp.) of six Common chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita sensu lato* taxa. For this network, sequences of 19 individuals (see Table 1) were used. Each circle represents unique CYTB sequence (haplotype) of 945 bp. The relative diameter of each circle is an indication of its frequency in total dataset (n=19). Numbers inside circles: number of times that a haplotype was observed. Circles without number: haplotypes that were found in one individual only. Small black dots: inferred (not observed) haplotypes necessary to construct the network. Short lines between circles without a number mark differences between two haplotypes on one position (out of 945 bp.), other longer lines mark two or more (as indicated by numbers along lines) different positions.

We subsequently combine both genes, separately, with the three additional short polymorphic mtDNA fragments (Figures 3 and 4). From these two combined mtDNA networks it is clear that both genes, when combined with the three additional fragments show a much better differentiation among the two different *brevirostris* groups and *caucasicus*. As a result of this we decided to screen all suspect *brevirostris/caucasicus* samples with these three additional mtDNA fragments in addition to the 945 bp. CYTB fragment.

Figure 3. Network of variation in the mtDNA ND2 gene (1040 bp.) combined with three shorter mtDNA fragments, ND1 (110 bp.), ATP8/ATP6 (240 bp.), and ND3/tRNA-ARG (125 bp.) of six Common chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita sensu lato* taxa. For this network, sequences of 19 individuals (see Table 1) were used. Each circle represents unique combined mtDNA sequence (haplotype) of 1515 bp. The relative diameter of each circle is an indication of its frequency in total dataset (n=19). Numbers inside circles: number of times that a haplotype was observed. Circles without number: haplotypes that were found in one individual only. Small black dots: inferred (not observed) haplotypes necessary to construct the network. Short lines between circles without a number mark differences between two haplotypes on one position (out of 1515 bp.), other longer lines mark two or more (as indicated by numbers along lines) different positions.

Figure 4. Network of variation in the mtDNA CYTB gene (945 bp.) combined with three shorter mtDNA fragments, ND1 (110 bp.), ATP8/ATP6 (240 bp.), and ND3/tRNA-ARG (125 bp.) of six Common chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita sensu lato* taxa. For this network, sequences of 19 individuals (see Table 1) were used. Each circle represents unique combined mtDNA sequence (haplotype) of 1420 bp. The relative diameter of each circle is an indication of its frequency in total dataset (n=19). Numbers inside circles: number of times that a haplotype was observed. Circles without number: haplotypes that were found in one individual only. Small black dots: inferred (not observed) haplotypes necessary to construct the network. Short lines between circles without a number mark differences between two haplotypes on one position (out of 1420 bp.), other longer lines mark two or more (as indicated by numbers along lines) different positions.

As a final step, we added the mtDNA sequence information (CYTB gene - 945 bp., ND1 - 110 bp., ATP8/ATP6 - 240 bp., ND3/tRNA-ARG - 125 bp.) from the six Dutch/German *brevirostris* or *caucasicus* individuals to the same sequences of the 19 reference individuals and repeated the Median Joining network analyses. The result is shown in Figure 5. From the network it is clear that five out of six individuals clustered with the *caucasicus* reference samples, whereas one sample clustered with the *brevirostris-2* reference samples. See the main paper for more information on the interpretation of these results.

Figure 5. Network of variation in the mtDNA CYTB gene (945 bp.) combined with three shorter mtDNA fragments, ND1 (110 bp.), ATP8/ATP6 (240 bp.), and ND3/tRNA-ARG (125 bp.) of six Common chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita sensu lato* taxa. For this network, sequences of 19 individuals (see Table 1) were used in addition to the six unidentified samples (shown as pale grey circles, indicated with a dark blue arrow). Each circle represents unique combined mtDNA sequence (haplotype) of 1420 bp. The relative diameter of each circle is an indication of its frequency in total dataset (n=19). Numbers inside circles: number of times that a haplotype was observed. Circles without number: haplotypes that were found in one individual only. Small black dots: inferred (not observed) haplotypes necessary to construct the network. Short lines between circles without a number mark differences between two haplotypes on one position (out of 1420 bp.), other longer lines mark two or more (as indicated by numbers along lines) different positions.

References

- Hall T.A. 1999. BioEdit: a user-friendly biological sequence alignment editor and analysis program for Windows 95/98/NT. Nucl Acids Symp Ser 1999; 41:95-98. Doi 10.14344/IOC.ML.14.1.
- Helbig AJ, Martens J, Seibold I, Henning F, Schottler B, Wink M. 1996. Phylogeny and species limits in the Palearctic chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita* complex: mitochondrial genetic differentiation and bioacoustics evidence. Ibis 138: 650–666. (<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1474-919X.1996.tb04767.x>)
- de Knijff P, de Leeuw R', te Raa M. 2024. Genetic research protocol for studying Chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita* s.l. taxa. Zenodo. (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11472174>)
- Marova I, Ilyina I, Kvartalnov P, Grabovsky V, Belokon M, Solovyova E, Ivanitskii V. 2021. From the Bosphorus to Kopet Dagh: morphological, genetic and bioacoustic variation in the Chiffchaff in Turkey, the Caucasus and western Turkmenistan. Ardea 109:1–16. (<https://doi.org/10.5253/arde.v109i3.a3>)

First records of *Phylloscopus collybita brevirostris* (Strickland, 1837) and *Ph. c. caucasicus* (Loskot, 1991) in north-western Europe

Raković M, Neto JM, Lopes RJ, Koblik EA, Fadeev IV, Lohman YV, Aghayan SA, Boano G, Pavia M, Perlman Y, Kiat Y, Ben Dov A, Collinson JM, Voelker G, Drovetski SV. 2019. Geographic patterns of mtDNA and Z-linked sequence variation in the Common Chiffchaff and the 'chiffchaff complex'. PLoS ONE 14(1): e0210268. (<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0210268>)

Supplementary information

Below we give the sequences of all five mtDNA fragments as obtained in all 19 reference samples (see Table 1). In this fast-format file the five fragments are separated by a single inserted empty space. The fragments are included in the following order: (1) ND1, 110bp.; (2) ND2, 1040 bp.; (3) ATP8/ATP6, 240 bp.; (4) ND3/tRNA-ARG, 125 bp.; (5) CYTB 945 bp.

We included the following reference samples: *Ph. c. collybita* (n=2), *Ph. c. abietinus* (n=2), *Ph. c. menzbieri* (n=3), *Ph. c. caucasicus* (n=3), *Ph. c. brevirostris* (n=3 from two different sequence clades, and *Ph. c. 'Mt Hermon'* (n=3) representing birds breeding in the Mt Hermon region of northern Israel displaying a very distinct mtDNA sequence. These birds very likely do not any longer represent a distinct subspecies. Instead, they very likely represent birds from a population carrying a once isolated mtDNA signature that is now swamped by other mtDNA lineages in this population.

```
>PhabiTT0096
AAAAATTC TAAGTTACATGCAAGGTCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTGTTGGCCATTTGGACT
GCTTCAACCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAAACATTCATCAAAGAGCCCATCC-ATGAACCC
CAAGCAAACTAATCTTCACCATCAGCCTTCTTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACAACCTCAAGC
AACCACCTGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGGCCTTGAATCAACACCCTCGCTATCCTCCACTA
ATCTCCAAATCCCACCATCCTCGAGCCATCGAAGCCGCAACCAAACTTTTTAGTACAA
GCAACTGCCTCTACTTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAAACCAACGCATGATATACCGGACAG
TGAGATATTACCAATTAACCCATCCCATCTCCTGCCTAATCCTAACCTCTGCCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTCCCATTCCACTTTTGATTCGCCGAAGTCCTTCAAGGAGCACCA
CTCACAACCGGGTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCAATCACATTATCTTTT
TTAACCTCTACTCTTTAAACCCAACTCTACTAAGTTCATAGCCATTCTCTCTGCTGCT
CTTGGCGGGTGAATAGGACTTAACCAGACCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTCTCTTCT
ATCGCCACCTTAGGCTGAATGACCATTATATCTCTTTTGACCCAAAACCTAACCTTACTG
AACTTCTACATCTACAGCCTCATAACTGCAGCCACTTTTCTAGCCCTAACTCAATCAAA
GCTTTAAAACCTAACACCCCTCATAACAACATGAACAAAACCTCCCTCATTAACGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCCTAGCAGGTCTCCCTCCCTCAGAGGCTTTCTGCCAAA
TGATTAATCATTCAAGAACTAAGCAAGCAAGCAAGCAAGCAAGCAAGCAAGCAAGCAAG
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCTATTTCTTTTACCTCCGTCGTCGACTACTGCACCACAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAATCAGATGAACAATGACACACTAACAAACCAACCCACATC
ACAATCGCCATTTTAACCACTCTATCTACTATACTTCTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCTAC
CCTTTATCATA-AAAACCTCAGCATTGTAACCAACCAACCCCTCCATCTAGCAAAACACC
CACAACCTCCAAACACAACCCCTGAACTGACCATGAACCTAAGCTTCTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATTCAGCCCTTA
TTAATCCCTCCCGAGTAACCGTGAATTACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCCCTACAATATGA
TTTATCAATCTA-AAGCAAGCCTTACCTTACTTAACTGAGCCATTTTAACTTCTT
CTCCTCACCCCTAGGACTTATCCAGCAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCTAGAAATGGGCTGAATAG
TAGAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTTGGATCCCTATTAGGAATCTGCTTAATCACACAAAT
TGTCACAGGACTACTATTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTCACTTC
TGTCGCCACACATGCGAAACGTTCAATTCGGCTGACTAATTCGAAACCTCCAGCAAA
TGGAGCCTCCTTTTCTTTATCTGTCATCTACTTCCATATCGGCCGAGGATTTCTACTACGG
ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAAACCTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTAAACATCATAGC
CACTGCCTTCGTCGGGTACGTATTACCTGAGGGCAAAATATCATTTCTGAGGGGCCACAGT
AATTACAAACCTATTCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTTGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGGCGGATTTCTCAGTAGACAACCCCACTCTAACTCGATTTCTTCCCTCCACTTCTCTTCT
CCCATTATCATTTGCAGGGCTCACCCCTAGTGCACCTAACCTACTACAGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTTAGGAATTCATCAGACTGCGACAAAATCCCATTCCACCCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATTTCTAGGCTTTGCACTCATACTAATCTCTCTTGCCCTCCCTAGCCCTATT
CTCACCTAACCTTACTAGGAGACCCGAAAACCTTACGCGCGGCCAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTATTTGCCTAGCCATCTACGATCTATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTGTAAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCTAGTCTCTTCCCTCTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTAAAACCTACGCTCAATAACTTTCCGTCCTCTCACAAATCCTATT
CTGAACCCCTAGTACCAACCTTCTCGTCTTAACCTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAACAGCCGAACA
CCCA
```

```
>PhabiTT0095
AAAAATTC TAAGTTACATGCAAGGTCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTGTTGGCCATTTGGACT
GCTTCAACCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAAACATTCATCAAAGAGCCCATCC-ATGAACCC
CAAGCAAACTAATCTTCACCATCAGCCTTCTTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACAACCTCAAGC
AACCACCTGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGGCCTTGAATCAACACCCTCGCTATCCTCCACTA
ATCTCCAAATCCCACCATCCTCGAGCCATCGAAGCCGCAACCAAACTTTTTAGTACAA
GCAACTGCCTCTACTTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAAACCAACGCATGATATACCGGACAG
TGAGATATTACCAATTAACCCATCCCATCTCCTGCCTAATCCTAACCTCTGCCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTCCCATTCCACTTTTGATTCGCCGAAGTCCTTCAAGGAGCACCA
CTCACAACCGGGTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCAATCACATTATCTTTT
TTAACCTCTACTCTTTAAACCCAACTCTACTAAGTTCATAGCCATTCTCTCTGCTGCT
CTTGGCGGGTGAATAGGACTTAACCAGACCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTCTCTTCT
ATCGCCACCTTAGGCTGAATGACCATTATATCTCTTTTGACCCAAAACCTAACCTTACTG
AACTTCTACATCTACAGCCTCATAACTGCAGCCACTTTTCTAGCCCTAACTCAATCAAA
GCTTTAAAACCTAACACCCCTCATAACAACATGAACAAAACCTCCCTCATTAACGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCCTAGCAGGTCTCCCTCCCTCAGAGGCTTTCTGCCAAA
TGATTAATCATTCAAGAACTAAGCAAGCAAGCAAGCAAGCAAGCAAGCAAGCAAGCAAG
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCTATTTCTTTTACCTCCGTCGTCGACTACTGCACCACAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAATCAGATGAACAATGACACACTAACAAACCAACCCACATC
ACAATCGCCATTTTAACCACTCTATCTACTATACTTCTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCTAC
CCTTTATCATA-AAAACCTCAGCATTGTAACCAACCAACCCCTCCATCTAGCAAAACACC
CACAACCTCCAAACACAACCCCTGAACTGACCATGAACCTAAGCTTCTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATTCAGCCCTTA
TTAATCCCTCCCGAGTAACCGTGAATTACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCCCTACAATATGA
TTTATCAATCTA-AAGCAAGCCTTACCTTACTTAACTGAGCCATTTTAACTTCTT
CTCCTCACCCCTAGGACTTATCCAGCAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCTAGAAATGGGCTGAATAG
TAGAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTTGGATCCCTATTAGGAATCTGCTTAATCACACAAAT
TGTCACAGGACTACTATTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTCACTTC
TGTCGCCACACATGCGAAACGTTCAATTCGGCTGACTAATTCGAAACCTCCAGCAAA
TGGAGCCTCCTTTTCTTTATCTGTCATCTACTTCCATATCGGCCGAGGATTTCTACTACGG
ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAAACCTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTAAACATCATAGC
CACTGCCTTCGTCGGGTACGTATTACCTGAGGGCAAAATATCATTTCTGAGGGGCCACAGT
AATTACAAACCTATTCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTTGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGGCGGATTTCTCAGTAGACAACCCCACTCTAACTCGATTTCTTCCCTCCACTTCTCTTCT
CCCATTATCATTTGCAGGGCTCACCCCTAGTGCACCTAACCTACTACAGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTTAGGAATTCATCAGACTGCGACAAAATCCCATTCCACCCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATTTCTAGGCTTTGCACTCATACTAATCTCTCTTGCCCTCCCTAGCCCTATT
CTCACCTAACCTTACTAGGAGACCCGAAAACCTTACGCGCGGCCAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTATTTGCCTAGCCATCTACGATCTATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTGTAAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCTAGTCTCTTCCCTCTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTAAAACCTACGCTCAATAACTTTCCGTCCTCTCACAAATCCTATT
CTGAACCCCTAGTACCAACCTTCTCGTCTTAACCTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAACAGCCGAACA
CCCA
```

CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCCTATTCTTTTACCTCCGTCTCGCATACTGCACCACAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAATACATGAAACAATGACACACTAACAAACCAACCCACATC
ACAATCGCCATTTTAACTACTCTATCTACTATACTTCTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCTAC
CCTTTATCATA-AAAACCTCCTAGCATTGTAACCACCAACCTCCATCTAGCAAAACACC
CACAACCCAAACACAACCCCTGAACTGACCATGAACCTAAGCTTCTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATCCAGCCTTA
TTAATCCCTCCCGAGGTAACCGTTGAATTACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCTACAATTATGA
TTTATCAATCTA-AAACAAGACCCTACCCTACTTAACTCTGAGCCACTATTTTAAATCTT
CTCCTCACCTTAGGACTTATCCACGAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCTAGAATGGGCTGAATAG
TAGAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTTGGATCCCTATTAGGAATCTGCTTAATCACACAAAT
TGTCACAGGACTACTATTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTCACTTC
TGTCGCCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTCGGCTGACTAATTCGAAACCTCCACGCAAA
TGGAGCCTCCTTTTCTTATCTGCATCTACTTCCATATCGGCCGAGGATTCTACTACGG
ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAAACCTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTAAACATCATAGC
TACTGCCTTCGTGGGTACGTATTACCCTGAGGGCAAATATCATTTCTGAGGGGCCACAGT
AATTACAACCTTATCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGGCGGATTCTCAGTAGACAACCCACTCTAACTCGATTCTTCGCCCTCCACTTCCTTCT
CCCATTCATCATTCGAGGGCTCACCCCTAGTGCACCTAACCTACTACAGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTAGGAATTCATCAGACTGCGCAAAAATCCCATTCACCCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATTCCTAGGCTTCGCACTCATACTAATCCTCCTTCGCTCCCTAGCCCTATT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGACCAGAAAATTCACGCCGGCAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTATTGGCTACGCCATCCTACGATCTATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTGACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCTAGTCTCTTCTCCTTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTCAAAACTAGCTCAATAACTTTCCGTCCCTCTCACAAATCCTATT
CTGAACCTTAGTACCAACCTTCTCGTCTAACTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAACCAGTCGAACA
CCCA

>Phcol1TT0049

AAAAATTCTAAGTTACATACAGGGTCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTGTTGGCCATTGGACT
GCTTCAACCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAAACCTATTCATCAAAAGAGCCCATCC-ATGAACCC
CAAGCAAACTAATCTTACCCTCAGCCTTCTTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACACCTCAAGC
AACCACTGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGGCCTTGAATCAACACCTCGCTATCCTCCACTA
ATCTCCAAATCCACCATCTCCTGAGCCATCGAAGCCGCAACCAATACTTTTATGACAA
GCAACTGCCTCTACTTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAACCAACGCATGATATACCGGACAG
TGAGATATTACCAATTAACCCACCCCTCTCCTGCCTAATCTAACCTCTGCCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTCCCATTTCCACTTTTGATTTCCCGAAGTCTTCAAGGAGCACA
CTCACACCGGGCTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCCCAATCACATTTCTTT
TTAACCTCTCACTCTTTAAACCCAACTCTACTAACTTGCCATAGCCATTCTCTCTGCT
CTTGGCGGATGAATAGGACTTAAACCAGACCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTCTCTTCT
ATCGCCACCTTAGGCTGAATGACCATTATTTATCTCTTTGACCCAAAACCTAACTTTACTG
AACTTCTACACTACAGCCTCATAACTGCAGCCACTTTCTAGCCCTAAACTCAATCAA
GCTTTAAAACCTAACCCCTCATAAACACATGAACAAAACCTCCCTCATTAACCGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCCTAGCAGGTCTCCTCCCTCACAGGCTTTCTGCCCAA
TGATTAATCATTAAGAATAACTAAGCAAAGCATAGCCCCAGCAGCAACCGTAATCTCC
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCCTATTCTTTTACCTCCGCTCGCATACTGCACCACAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAATGATATCAGATGAAACAATGACATACTAACAAAACCAACCCACAT
ACAATCGCCATTTTAAACCCCTATCTACTATACTTCTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCTAC
CCTTTATCATA-AAAACCTTAGCATTTGTAACCACCAACCCCCATCTAGCAAAACACC
CACAACTCCAAACACAACCCCTGAACCTGACCATGAACCTAAGCTTCTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATTCAGCCCTTA
TTAATCCCTCCCGAGGTAACCGTTGAATTACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCTACAATTATGA
CTTATCAATCTA-AACAAGACCCTACCTACTTAACTCTGAGCCACTATTTTAAATCTT
CTCCTCACCTTAGGACTTATCCACGAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCTAGAATGAGCTGAATAG
TAGAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTTGGATCCCTATTAGGAATCTGCTTAATCACACAAAT
TGTCACAGGACTATTACTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTCACTTC
TGTCGCCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTCGGCTGACTAATTCGAAACCTCCACGCAAA
CGGAGCCTCCTTTTCTTATCTGCATCTACTTCCATATCGGCCGAGGATTCTACTACGG
ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAAACCTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTAACACTCATAGC
CACTGCCTTCGTGGGTACGTATTACCCTGAGGGCAAATATCATTTCTGAGGGGCCACAGT
AATTACAACCTTATCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGGCGGATTCTCAGTAGACAACCCACCTAACTCGATTCTTCGCCCTCCACTTCCTTCT
CCCATTCATCATTCGAGGGCTCACCCCTAGTGCACCTAACCTACTACAGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTAGGAATTCATCAGACTGCGCAAAAATCCCATTCACCCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATTCCTAGGCTTCGCACTCATACTAATCCTCCTTCGCTCCCTAGCCCTATT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGACCAGAAAATTCACGCCGGCAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTTAACTTTGCTACGCCATCCTACGATCTATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGCTACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCTAGTCTCTTCTCCTTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTCAAAACTAGCTCAATAACTTTCCGTCCCTCTCACAAATCCTATT
CTGAACCTTAGTACCAACCTTCTCGTCTAACTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAACCAGTCGAACA
CCCA

>Phcol1TT0116

AAAAATTCTAAGTTACATGACAGGGTCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTGTTGGCCATTGGACT
GCTTCAACCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAAACCTATTCATCAAAAGAGCCCATCC-ATGAACCC
CAAGCAAACTAATCTTACCCTCAGCCTTCTTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACACCTCAAGC
AACCACTGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGGCCTTGAATCAACACCTCGCTATCCTCCACTA
ATCTCCAAATCCACCATCTCCTGAGCCATCGAAGCCGCAACCAATACTTTTATGACAA
GCAACTGCCTCTACTTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAACCAACGCATGATATACCGGACAG

First records of *Phylloscopus collybita brevirostris* (Strickland, 1837) and *Ph. c. caucasicus* (Loskot, 1991) in north-western Europe

TGAGATATTACCCAATTAACCCACCCCATCTCCTGCCTAATCCTAACCTCTGCCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTCCCATCCACTTTTGATTCCCCGAAGTCCTTCAAGGAGCACCA
CTCACAACCGGGTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCCAATCACATTATTCTTT
TTAACCTCTCACTCTTTAAACCCATCTAACAACATGAACAAAACTCCCTCATTAACGCAATA
CTTGGCGGATGAATAGGACTTAACCAGACCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTCTCTTCT
ATCGCCACCTAGGCTGAATGACCATTATATCTCTTTGACCCAAAACCTAACCTTACTG
AACTTCTACATCTACAGCCTCATAACTGCAGCCACTTTTCTAGCCCTAAACTCAATCAAA
GCTTTAAACTAACAACCCCTCATAACAACATGAACAAAACTCCCTCATTAACGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCCTAGCAGGTCTCCCTCCCTCAGAGGCTTTCTGCCAAA
TGATTAATCATTCAAGAATAACTAAGCAAAGCATAGCCCCAGCAGCAACCGTAATCTCC
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCTATTCTTTTACCTCCGCTCGCATACTGCACCACAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAATCAGATGAAACAATGACATACTAACAAAAACCCACATC
ACAATCGCCATTTTAACCACCCCTATCTACTATACTTCTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCTAC
CCTTTATCATA-AAAACCTTAGCATTGTAAACCACCAACCCCCATCTAGCAAAACACC
CACAACCTCAAACACAACCCCTGAACCTGACCATGAACCTAAGCTTCTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATTTCCAGCCTTA
TTAATCCCTCCCGAGGTAACCGTTGAATTACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCTACAATTATGA
CTTATCAATCTA-AACAAGACCTACCTCTACTTAACTCTGAGCCACTATTTTAACTCTT
CTCCTCACCTTAGGACTTATCCACGAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCTAGAAATGAGCTGAATAG
TAGAAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTCGGATCCCTATTAGGAATCTGCTTAACTCACAAAA
TGTCACAGGACTATTACTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTACCTC
TGTCGCCCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTCCGCTGACTAATTCGAAACCTCCACGCAA
CGGAGCCTCCTTTTCTTATCTGCATCTACTCCATATCGGGCCGAGGATTCTACTACGG
ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAACCTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCTACTATTAAACATCATAGC
CACTGCCTTCGTCGGGTACGTATTACCCTGAGGGCAAATATCATTTCTGAGGGGCCACAGT
AATTACAAACCTATTCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGGCGGATTTCTCAGTAGACAACCCACCCCTAACCTCGATTCTTCGCCCTCCACTTCCTTCT
CCCATTCATCATTCGAGGCTCACCCCTAGTGCACCTAACCTACTACACGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTTAGGAATTCATCAGACTGCGACAAAAATCCCATTTCCACCCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATTTCTAGGCTTCGCACTCATACTAATCTCCTTGCTCCCTAGCCCTATT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGACCCAGAAAACTTACGCGCGCCAAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAAATGATATTTCTATTGCTTACGCAATCCCTAGCATCTATGCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGCGTACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCTAGTCTCTTTCTCCTTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTCGAAACTAGCTCAATAACTTTCCGCTCCCTCTCACAAATCCTATT
CTGAACCTTAGTAGCCACCTTCTCGTCTAATTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAACAGTCGAACA
CCCA

>TT0280BRE1

AAAAATCTAAGTTACATGCAAGGTCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTGTTGGCCATTGGACT
GCTTCAACCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAAACATATTCATCAAAGAGCCCATCC-ATGAACCC
CAAGCAAACTAATCTTACCATCAGCCTTCTTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACAACTCAAGC
AACCACTGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGCTTGAATTAACACCCCTCGCTATCCTCCCACTA
ATCTCAAATCCACCATCTCGAGCCATCGAAGCCGCACTAAATACCTTTTCTAGTACAA
GCAACTGCCTCTACTTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAACCAACGCATGATATACCGGACAG
TGAGATATTACCAATTAACCCACCCCATCTCCTGCCTAATTTAACCTCTGCCATTGCA
ATAAACTTAGGACTAGTCCCATTTCCACTTTTGATTTCCCGAAGTCCTTCAAGGAGCACA
CTCACAACCGGGTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCCAATCACATTATTCTTT
TTAACCTCTCACTCTTTAAACCCAACTCTACTAACTTGATAGCCATTCTCTCTGCTGCT
CTTGGCGGGTGAATAGGACTTAACCAGACCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTCTCTTCT
ATCGCCACCTTAGGCTAGACTGACCATTATATCTCTTTTGAACCAAACTAACTTTACTG
AACTTCTACATCTACAGCCTCATAACTACAGCCACTTTTCTAGCCCTAAACTCAATCAAA
GCTTTAAACTAACAACCCCTCATAACAACATGAACAAAACTCCCTCATTAACGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCCTGGCAGGTCTCCCTCCCTCAGAGGCTTTCTGCCAAA
TGATTAATCATTCAAGAATAACTAAGCAAAGCATAGCCCCAGCAGCAACCGTAATCTCC
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCTATTCTTTTACCTCCGCTCGCATACTGCACCACAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAATCAGATGAAACAATGACACACTAACAAAAACCCACATC
ACAATCGCTATTTAACCCTCTATCTACTATACTTCTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCTAC
CCTTTATCATA-AAAACCTTAGCATTGTAAACCACCAACCCCTCCATCTAGCAAAACACC
CACAACCTCAAACACAACCCCTGAACCTGACCATGAACCTAAGCTTCTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATTTCCAGCCTTA
CTAATCCCTCCCGAGGTAACCGTTGAATTACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCTACAATTATGA
TTTATCAACCTA-AACAAGACCCCTACCTCTACTTTAATCTGAGCCACTATTTTAACTCT
CTCCTCACCCCTAGGACTTATCCACGAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCTAGAAATGAGCTGAATAG
TAGAAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTCGGATCCCTACTAGGAATCTGCTTAACTCACAAAA
TGTCACAGGACTATTACTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTACTTC
TGTCGCCCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTCCGCTGACTAATTCGAAACCTCCACGCAA
TGGAGCCTCCTTTTCTTATCTGCATCTACTTCCATATCGGGCCGAGGATTCTACTACGG
ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAACCTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTAACTTATAGC
CACTGCCTTCGTCGGGTACGTATTACCCTGAGGGCAAATATCATTTCTGAGGAGCTACAGT
AATTACAAACCTATTCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGGCGGATTTCTCAGTAGACAACCCACTCTAACCTCGATTCTTCGCCCTCCACTTCCTTCT
CCCATTCATCATTCGAGGCTCACCCCTAGTGCACCTAACTCTACTACACGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTTAGGAATTCATCAGACTGCGACAAAAATCCCATTTCCACCCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATTTCTAGGCTTCGCACTCATACTAATCTCCTTGCTCCCTAGCTCTATT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGACCCAGAAAAATTTACGCGCGCCAAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAAATGATATTTCTATTGCTTACGCAATCCCTAGCATCTATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTGACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCTAGTCTCTTCTCCTTCC

First records of *Phylloscopus collybita brevirostris* (Strickland, 1837) and *Ph. c. caucasicus* (Loskot, 1991) in north-western Europe

CCTCCTCCACACTTCAAACACTACGCTCAATAACTTTCCGTCCCTCTCACAAATCCTATT
CTGAACCCCTAGTAGCCAACTTCTCGTCTTAACCTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAACCCAGTCGAACA
CCCA

>TT0070BRE1

AAAAATCTAAGTTACATGCAAGGTCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTTGTTGGCCATTTGGACT
GCTTCAACCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAAACCTATTCATCAAAGAGCCCATCC-ATGAACCC
CAAGCAAACTAATCTTACCATCAGCCTTCTTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACAACCTCAAGC
AACCACGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGGCCTTGAATCAACACCCCTCGCTATCCTCCCAC
ATCTCCAAATCCCACCATCTCGAGCCATCGAAGCCGCAACTAAATACTTTTTAGTACAA
GCAACTGCCTCTACTTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAAACCACGCATGATATACCGGACAG
TGAGATATTACCAATTAACCCACCCCATCTCCTGCCTAATTTAACCCTTGCCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTCCATTCACCTTTTGATTTCCCGAAGTCCTTCAAGGAGCACCA
CTCACAACCGGGTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCAATCACATTATCTTT
TTAACCTCTACTCTTTAAACCCAACTCTACTAAGTTCATAGCCATTCTCTCTGCTGCT
CTTGGCGGGTGAATAGGACTTAACCAGACCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTCTCTTCT
ATCGCCACCTAGGCTGAATGACCATTATATCTCTTTTGACCCAAAATAACTTTACTG
AACTTCTACATCTACAGCCTCATAACTACAGCCACTTTTCTAGCCCTAACTCAATCAAA
GCTTTAAACTTACAACCTCATAACAACATGAACAAAACTCCCTCATTAACGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCCTGGCAGGTCTCCCTCCCTCAGAGCTTTCTGCCAAA
TGATTAATCATTCAAGAACTAATAAGCAAAGCATAGCCCCAGCAGCAACCGTAATCTCC
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCCTATCTTTTACCTCCGCTCGCATACTGCACCACAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAATACATGAACAATGACACACTAACAAACCAACCCACATC
ACAATCGTATTTTAAACCTCTATCTACTATACTTCTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCTAC
CCTTTATCATA-AAAACCTTCTAGCATTGTAACCAACCCCTCCATCTAGCAAAACACC
CACAACCTCAAACACAACCCCTGAACTGACCATGAACCTTAAGCTTCTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATTCAGCCTTA
CTAATCCCTCCCGAGGTAACCGTTGAATTACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCTACAATATGA
TTTATCAACCTA-AACAAGACCTACCTCTACTTTAATCTGAGCCACTTTTTAATCTCT
CTCCTCACCTTAGGACTTATCCACGAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCTAGAAATGAGCTGAATAG
TAGAAAGTTAGTCTAAGT-AACTTCGGATCCCTACTAGGAATCTGCTTAATCACA
TGTACAGGACTATTACTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATCACTTC
TGTCGCCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTCGGCTGACTAATTCGAAACCTCCACGCAA
TGGAGCCTCCTTTTTCTTTATCTGCATCTACTTCCATATCGGCCGAGGATTCTACTACGG
ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAAACCTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTAACACTTATAGC
CACTGCCTTCGTGGGTACGTATTACCTGAGGGCAAATATCATTTCTGAGGAGTACAGT
AATTACAACCTATTCTAGCAATCCCATACATTTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGGCGGATTCTCAGTAGACAACCCCACTTAACCTCGATTCTTCGCCCTCCACTTCCTTCT
CCCATTATCATTGACAGGCTCACCTTAGTGCACCTAATCTACTACAGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTAGGAATTCATCAGACTGCGCAAAAAATCCCATTTCCACCCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATTTCTAGGCTTCGCATCATACTAATCTCCTTTGCCTCCCTAGCTCTATT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGACCCAGAAAAATTTACGCGGCCAAACCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTATTTGCCTAGCCATCCTACGATCTATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTGACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCTAGTCTCTCTCCCTTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTCAAACCTACGCTCAATAACTTTCCGTCCCTCTCACAAATCCTATT
CTGAACCCCTAGTAGCCAACTTCTCGTCTTAACCTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAACCCAGTCGAACA
CCCA

>TT0075BRE1

AAAAATCTAAGTTACATGCAAGGTCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTTGTTGGCCATTTGGACT
GCTTCAACCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAAACCTATTCATCAAAGAGCCCATCC-ATGAACCC
CAAGCAAACTAATCTTACCATCAGCCTTCTTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACAACCTCAAGC
AACCACGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGGCCTTGAATCAACACCCCTCGCTATCCTCCCAC
ATCTCCAAATCCCACCATCTCGAGCCATCGAAGCCGCAACTAAATACTTTTTAGTACAA
GCAACTGCCTCTACTTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAAACCACGCATGATATACCGGACAG
TGAGATATTACCAATTAACCCACCCCATCTCCTGCCTAATTTAACCCTTGCCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTCCATTCACCTTTTGATTTCCCGAAGTCCTTCAAGGAGCACCA
CTCACAACCGGGTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCAATCACATTATCTTT
TTAACCTCTACTCTTTTAAACCCAACTCTACTAACCCTGATAGCCATTCTCTCTGCTGCT
CTTGGCGGGTGAATAGGACTTAACCAGACCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTCTCTTCT
ATCGCCACCTAGGCTGAATGACCATTATATCTCTTTTGACCCAAAATAACTTTACTG
AACTTCTACATCTACAGCCTCATAACTACAGCCACTTTTCTAGCCCTAACTCAATCAAA
GCTTTAAACTTACAACCTCATAACAACATGAACAAAACTCCCTCATTAACGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCCTGGCAGGTCTCCCTCCCTCAGAGCTTTCTGCCAAA
TGATTAATCATTCAAGAACTAATAAGCAAAGCATAGCCCCAGCAGCAACCGTAATCTCC
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCCTATCTTTTACCTCCGCTCGCATACTGCACCACAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAATACATGAACAATGACACACTAACAAACCAACCCACATC
ACAATCGTATTTTAAACCTCTATCTACTATACTTCTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCTAC
CCTTTATCATA-AAAACCTTCTAGCATTGTAACCAACCCCTCCATCTAGCAAAACACC
CACAACCTCAAACACAACCCCTGAACTGACCATGAACCTTAAGCTTCTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATTCAGCCTTA
CTAATCCCTCCCGAGGTAACCGTTGAATTACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCTACAATATGA
TTTATCAACCTA-AACAAGACCTACCTCTACTTTAATCTGAGCCACTTTTTAATCTCT
CTCCTCACCTTAGGACTTATCCACGAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCTAGAAATGAGCTGAATAG
TAGAAAGTTAGTCTAAGT-AACTTCGGATCCCTACTAGGAATCTGCTTAATCACA
TGTACAGGACTATTACTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATCACTTC
TGTCGCCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTCGGCTGACTAATTCGAAACCTCCACGCAA
TGGAGCCTCCTTTTTCTTTATCTGCATCTACTTCCATATCGGCCGAGGATTCTACTACGG

First records of *Phylloscopus collybita brevirostris* (Strickland, 1837) and *Ph. c. caucasicus* (Loskot, 1991) in north-western Europe

ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAAACCTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTAAACACTTATAGC
CACTGCCTTCGTGGGTACGTATTACCCCTGAGGGCAAATATCATTTCTGAGGAGCTACAGT
AATTACAAACCTATTCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGCGGGATTCTCAGTAGACAACCCCACTCTAACTCGATTCTTCGCCCTCCACTTCCTTCT
CCCATTTCATCATTGCAGGGCTCACCCCTAGTGCACCTAACTCTACTACACGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTAGGAATTCATCAGACTGCGACAAAATCCCATTCCACCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATTTAGGCTTCGCACCTACTAATACTCCTTCCTGCCTCCCTAGCTCTATT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGACCCAGAAAATTTACGCGGGCAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTATTTCCTACGCCATCCTACGATCTATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCCTAGTCTCTCCCTCCTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTCAAACCTACGCTCAATAACTTTCCGTCCCTCTCACAAATCCTATT
CTGAACCTTAGTAGCCAACTTCTCGTCTAACTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAACCAGTCGAACA
CCCA

>TT0073BRE2

AAAAATCTAAGTTACATGCAAGGTGCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTGTTGGCCATTTGGACT
GCTTCAACCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAAACCTATTTCATCAAGAGGCCATCC-ATGAACCC
CAAGCAAACTAATCTTACCATCAGCCTTCTTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACACCTCAAGC
AACCACCTGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGGCCTTGAATCAACACCCCTCGCTATCCTCCACTA
ATCTCCAAATCCCACCATCTCGAGCCATCGAAGCCGCAACTAAATACTTTTTAGTACAA
GCAACTGCCTTACTTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAACCAACGCATGATATACGGACAG
TGAGATATTACCAATTAACCCACCCCATCTCCTGCCTAATTTAACCCTGCCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTCCATTCACCTTTTGATTTCCCGAAGTCCTTCAAGGAGCACCA
CTCACAACCGGGTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCAATCACATTATCTTTT
TTAACCCTTCACTCTTTAGACCCCACTACTAACTTGATAGCCATTCTCTGCTGCT
CTTGGCGGGTGAATAGGACTTAACCAGACCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTCTCTTCT
ATCGCCACCTAGGCTGAATGACCATTATATCTCTTTTGACCCAAAACCTAATTTACTG
AACTTCTACATCTACAGCCTCATAACTACAGCCACTTTTCTAGCCCTAAACTCAATCAA
GCTTTAAAACCTAACACCCCTCATAACAACATGAACAAAACCTCCCTCATTAAACGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCCTGGCAGGTCTCCCTCCCTCAGAGCTTTCTGCCAAA
TGATTAATCATTCAAGAATAACTAAGCAAAGCATAGCCCCAGCAGCAACCGTAATCTCC
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCTATCTTTTACCTCCGCTCGCATACTGCACCACAAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAATACATGAACAATGACACACTAACAAAACCAACCACATC
ACAATCGTATTTTAACCACTCTATCCACTATACTTCTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCTAC
CCTTTATCATA-AAAACCTTAGCATTTGTAACCACCAACCCTCCATCTAGCAAAACACC
CACAACCTCAAACACACACCCCTGAACTGACCATGAACTTAAGCTTCTTCGACCAATTC
CAAGCCCTCCCTTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATTCCAGCCTTA
TTAATCCCTCCCGAGTAACCGTTGAATTACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCCTACAACATATGA
TTTATCAACCTA-AACAAGACCTACCTTACTTTAATCTGAGCCACTATTTTAAATCTT
CTCCTCACCTTAGGACTTATCCAGAAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCTTAGAATGAGCTGAATAG
TAGAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTCGGATCCCTACTAGGAATCTGCTTAATCACACAAAT
TGTCACAGGACTATTACTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTCACTTC
TGTCGCCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTCGGCTGACTAATCCGAAACCTCCAGCAAA
TGGAGCCTCCTTTTCTTTATCTGCATCTACTTCCATATCGGCCGAGGATTTCTACTACGG
ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAAACCTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCTACTATTAACACTCATAGC
CACTGCCTTCGTGGGTAGCTAATTACCTGAGGGCAAATATCATTTCTGAGGAGCTACAGT
AATTACAAACCTATTCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGCGGGATTCTCAGTAGACAACCCCACTCTAACTCGATTCTTCGCCCTCCACTTCCTCCT
CCCATTTCATCATTGAGGGCTCACCCCTAGTGCACCTAACTCTACTACACGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTAGGAATTCATCAGACTGCGACAAAATCCCATTCCACCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATTTAGGCTTCGCACCTACTAATACTCCTTCCTGCCTCCCTAGCTCTATT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGACCCAGAAAACCTTACGCGGGCAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTATTTCCTACGCTATCTACGATCTATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCCTAGTCTCTCTCCCTCCTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTCAAACCTACGCTCAATAACTTTCCGTCCCTCTCACAAATCCTATT
CTGAACCTTAGTAGCCAACTTCTCGTCTAACTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAACCAGTCGAACA
CCCA

>TT0274BRE2

AAAAATCTAAGTTACATGCAAGGTGCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTGTTGGCCATTTGGACT
GCTTCAACCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAAACCTATTTCATCAAGAGGCCATCC-ATGAACCC
CAAGCAAACTAATCTTACCATCAGCCTTCTTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACACCTCAAGC
AACCACCTGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGGCCTTGAATCAACACCCCTCGCTATCCTCCACTA
ATCTCCAAATCCCACCATCTCGAGCCATCGAAGCCGCAACTAAATACTTTTTAGTACAA
GCAACTGCCTTACTTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAACCAACGCATGATATACGGACAG
TGAGATATTACCAATTAACCCACCCCATCTCCTGCCTAATTTAACCCTGCCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTCCACTTCCACTTTTGATTTCCCGAAGTCCTTCAAGGAGCACCA
CTCACAACCGGGTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCAATCACATTATCTTTT
TTAACCCTTCACTCTTTAGACCCCACTACTAACTTGATAGCCATTCTCTCTGCTGCT
CTTGGCGGGTGAATAGGACTTAACCAGACCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTCTCTTCT
ATCGCCACCTAGGCTGAATGACCATTATATCTCTTTTGACCCAAAACCTAATTTACTG
AACTTCTACATCTACAGCCTCATAACTACAGCCACTTTTCTAGCCCTAAACTCAATCAA
GCTTTAAAACCTAACACCCCTCATAACAACATGAACAAAACCTCCCTCATTAAACGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCCTGGCAGGTCTCCCTCCCTCAGAGCTTTCTGCCAAA
TGATTAATCATTCAAGAATAACTAAGCAAAGCATAGCCCCAGCAGCAACCGTAATCTCC
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCTATCTTTTACCTCCGCTCGCATACTGCACCACAAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAATACATGAACAATGACACACTAACAAAACCAACCACATC
ACAATCGTATTTTAACCACTCTATCCACTATACTTCTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCTAC

First records of *Phylloscopus collybita brevirostris* (Strickland, 1837) and *Ph. c. caucasicus* (Loskot, 1991) in north-western Europe

CCTTTATCATA-AAAACCTCTAGCATTGTAAACCACCAACCCTCCATCTAGCAAAACACC
CACAACCTCAAACACAACCCCTGAACCTGACCATGAACCTTAAGCTTCTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATTCCCAGCCTTA
TTAATCCCCTCCCAGGTACCGTGAATTAACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCTACAACATATGA
TTTATCAACCTA-AACAAGACCTACCTCTACTTTAATCTGAGCCACTATTTAATTCTT
CTCCTCACCTTAGGACTTATCCACGAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCC TAGAATGAGCTGAATAG
TAGAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTCGGATCCCTACTAGGAATCTGCTTAATCACACAAAT
TGTCACAGGACTATTACTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTCACCTC
TGTCGCCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTTCGGCTGACTAATTCGAAACCTCCACGCAA
TGGAGCCTCCTTTTCTTATCTGCATCTACTTCCATATCGGCCGAGGATCTACTACGG
ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAAACCTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTAACACTCATAGC
CACTGCCCTTCGTGGGTACGTATTACCTGAGGGCAAATATCATCTGAGGAGCTACAGT
AATTACAAACCTATTCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGGCGGATTTCTCAGTAGACAACCCACTTAACCTCGATCTTTCGCCCTCCACTTCTCCT
CCCATTTCATTTGACGGGCTCACCTAGTGCACCTAACTCTACTACAGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTAGGAATTCATCAGACTGCGACAAAATCCCATTCCACCCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATTCTAGGCTTCGCACTCATACTAATCCTCCTTGCTCCCTAGCTCTATT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGACCAGAAAACCTCAGCGCGCCAAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTATTTGCCTACGCTATCTACGATCTATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCTAGTCTCTTCCCTCCCTTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTCAAACCTACGCTCAATAACTTTCCGTCCTCTCACAAATCCTATT
CTGAACCTTAGTAGCAACCTTCTCGTCTAATTGAGTAGGAAGCCAACCCAGTCGAACA
CCCA

>TT0279BRE2

AAAAATCTAAGTTACATGCAAGGTCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTGTTGGCCATTTGGACT
GCTTCAACCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAAACCTATTTCATCAAGAGGCCATCC-ATGAACCC
CAAGCAAACTAATCTTACCATCAGCCTTCTTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACAACCTCAAGC
AACCCATGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGCTTGAATCAACACCCCTCGCTATCCTCCACTA
ATCTCCAAATCCCACCATCCTCGAGCCATCGAAGCCGCAACTAAATACTTTTTAGTACAA
GCAACTGCCTCTACTTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAACCAACGCATGATATACCGGACAG
TGAGATATTACCAATTAACCCACCCATCTCCTGCCTAATTTAACCTCTGCCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTCCCATTCACACTTTTGATTTCCCGAAGTCCTTCAAGGAGCACA
CTCACAACCGGGTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCCAATCACATTATTTCTT
TTAACCTCTACTTTTAGACCCAACTCTACTAATTTGATAGCCATTCTCTCTGCTGCT
CTTGGCGGGTGAATAGGACTTAACCCAGCCAGATCCGAAAATCCTAGCTTTCTCTTCT
ATCGCCACCTTAGGCTGAATGACCATTAATCTCTTTTACCCGCAAACTAATTTACTG
AACTTCTACATCTACAGCCTCATAACTACAGCCACTTTTCTAGCCCTAAACTCAATCAA
GCTTTAAACTAACAACCTCATAACAACATGAACAAAACCTCCCTCATTAAACGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCCTGGCAGGTCTCCCTCCCTCACAGGCTTTCTGCCAAA
TGATTAATCATCAAGAACTAATAGCAAAGCATAGCCCCAGCAGCAACCGTAATCTCC
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCTAATTTCTTTTACCTCCGCTCGCATACTGCACAAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAATCAGTGAACAATGACACACTAACAAACCAACCCACATC
ACAATCGCTATTTAACCCTCTATCCACTATACTTTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCTAC
CCTTTATCATA-AAAACCTCTAGCATTGTAAACCACCAACCCTCCATCTAGCAAAACACC
CACAACCTCAAACACAACCCCTGAACCTGACCATGAACCTTAAGCTTCTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATTTCCCAGCCTTA
TTAATCCCCTCCCAGGTAACCGTGAATTAACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCTACAACATATGA
TTTATCAACCTA-AACAAGACCTACCTCTACTTTAATCTGAGCCACTATTTAATTTCT
CTCCTCACCTTAGGACTTATCCACGAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCC TAGAATGAGCTGAATAG
TAGAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTCGGATCCCTACTAGGAATCTGCTTAATCACACAAAT
TGTCACAGGACTATTACTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTCACCTC
TGTCGCCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTTCGGCTGACTAATTCGAAACCTCCACGCAA
TGGAGCCTCCTTTTCTTTATCTGCATCTACTTCCATATCGGCCGAGGATCTACTACGG
ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAAACCTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTAACACTCATAGC
CACTGCCCTTCGTGGGTACGTATTACCTGAGGGCAAATATCATTTCTGAGGAGCTACAGT
AATTACAAACCTATTCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGGCGGATTTCTCAGTAGACAACCCCACTTAACCTCGATTTCTTCGCCCTCCACTTCTCCT
CCCATTTCATTTGACGGGCTCACCTAGTGCACCTAACTCTACTACAGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTAGGAATTCATCAGACTGCGACAAAATCCCATTCCACCCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATTCTAGGCTTCGCACTCATACTAATCCTCCTTGCTCCCTAGCTCTATT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGTACGAAAACCTTACGCGCGCCAAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTATTTGCCTACGCTATCTACGATCTATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCTAGTCTCTTCCCTCCCTTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTCAAACCTACGCTCAATAACTTTCCGTCCTCTCACAAATCCTATT
CTGAACCTTAGTAGCAACCTTCTCGTCTAATTGAGTAGGAAGCCAACCCAGTCGAACA
CCCA

>TT043CAUC

AAAAATCTAAGTTACATGCAAGGTCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTGTTGGCCATTTGGACT
GCTTCAACCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAAACCTATTTCATCAAGAGGCCATCC-ATGAACCC
CAAGCAAACTAATCTTACCATCAGCCTTCTTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACAACCTCAAGC
AACCCATGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGCTTGAATCAACACCCCTCGCTATCCTCCACTA
ATCTCCAAATCCCACCATCCTCGAGCCATCGAAGCCGCAACTAAATACTTTTTAGTACAA
GCAACTGCCTCTACTTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAACCAACGCATGATATACCGGACAG
TGAGATATTACCAATTAACCCACCCATCTCCTGCCTAATTTAACCTCTGCCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTCCCATTCACACTTTTGATTTCCCGAAGTCCTTCAAGGAGCACA
CTCACAACCGGGTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCCAATCACATTATTTCTT

First records of *Phylloscopus collybita brevirostris* (Strickland, 1837) and *Ph. c. caucasicus* (Loskot, 1991) in north-western Europe

TTAACCTCTACTCTTTAAACCAACTCTACTAACCTGCATAGCCATTCTCTCTGCTGCT
CTTGGCGGGTGAATAGGACTTAACCAGACCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTCTCTTCT
ATCGCCACCTTAGGCTGAATGACCATTATATCTCTTTTGACCCAAAATAACTTTACTG
AACTTCTACACTCTACAGCCTATAAATACAGCCACTTTCTAGCCCTAAACTCAATCAAA
GCTTTAAACTAACAACCTCATAACAACATGAACAAAACTCCCTCATTAACGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCCTGGCAGGTCTCCCTCCCTCACAGGCTTTCTGCCAAA
TGATTAATCATTCAGGAATACTAAGCAAAGCATAGCCCCAGCAGCAACCGTAATCTCC
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCTTATCTTTTACCTCCGCTCGCATACTGCACCACAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAATACATGAACAATGACACACTAACAAACCAACCCACATC
ACAATCGTATTTAACCCTCTATCTACTATACTTCTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCTAC
CCTTTATCATA-AAAACCTCTAGCATTGTAAACCACCAACCTCCATCTAGCAAAACACC
CACAACTCCAAACACAACCCCTGAACCTGACCATGAACCTAAGCTTTTTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATTCCCAGCCTTA
TTAATCCCTCCCGAGTAAACGTTGAATTACAGCCGCTCTCCACCTACAATATGA
TTTATCAACCTA-AACAAGACCTACCTCTACTTTAATCTGAGCCACTATTTAATCTT
CTCCTCACCTTAGGACTTCCACGAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCTAGAATGAGCTGAATAG
TGGAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTCGGATCCCTACTAGGAATCTGCTTAATCACACAAAT
TGTCACAGGACTATTACTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTCACTTC
TGTCGCCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTCGGCTGACTAATTCGAAACCTCCACGCAAA
TGGAGCCTCCTTTTCTTTATCTGCATCTACTTCCATATCGGCCGAGGATTCTACTACGG
ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAAACCTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTAACACTCATAGC
CACTGCCTTCGTGGGTACGTATTACCTGAGGCAAAATATCATCTGAGGAGTACAGT
AATTACAAACCTATTCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGGCGGATTTCTCAGTAGACAACCCCACTTAACCTCGATTCTTGCCCTCCACTTCTTCT
CCCATTTCGTATTGACGGCTCACCCCTAGTGCACCTAACTCTACTACAGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTAGGAATTCATCAGACTGCGACAAAAATCCCATTCACCCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATTCTAGGCTTCGCACCTACTACTAATCTCCTTGCCCTCCCTAGCTTATT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGACCCAGAAAACCTCACGCCGCAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTATTTCGCTACGCCATCTACGATCTATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTGACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCTAGTCTCTTCCCTCTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTCAAACTACGCTCAATAACTTTCCGTCCTCTCACAAATCCTATT
CTGAACCTTAGTAGCCAACCTTCTCGTCTAACTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAACCCAGTCGAACA
CCCA

>TT0686CAUC

AAAAATCTAAGTTACATGCAAGGTGAAAAGGCCCAACATTGTTGGCCATTTGGACT
GCTTCAGCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAACTATTATCAAAAGAACCATCC-ATGAACCC
CAAGCAAAACTAATCTTACCATCAGCCTTCTTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACAACCTCAAGC
AACCACTGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGGCTTGAATCAACACCTCGCTATCCTCCACTA
ATCTCCAAATCCACCATCTCGAGCCTCGAAGCCGCAACTAAATACTTTTTAGTACAA
GCAACTGCCTCTACTTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAACCAACGCATGATATACCGGACAG
TGAGATATTACCCAATTAACCCACCCCATCTCCTGCTTAATTTAACCCTTGCCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTCCATTCCACTTTTGATTTCCCGAAGTCTTCAAGGAGCACC
CTCACAAACCGGCTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCCCAATCACATTATCTTT
TTAACCTCTACTCTTTAAACCCAACTCTACTAATCTGCATAGCCATTCTCTGTGCT
CTTGGCGGGTGAATAGGACTTAACCCAGCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTCTCTTCT
ATCGCCACCTTAGGCTGAATGACCATTATATCTCTTTTGACCCAAAATAACTTTACTG
AACTTCTACATCTACAGCCTCATAAATACAGCCACTTTTCTAGCCCTAAACTCAATCAAA
GCTTTAAACTAACAACCTCATAAACAACATGAACAAAACTCCCTCATTAACGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCCTGGCAGGTCTCCCTCCCTCACAGGCTTTCTGCCAAA
TGATTAATCATTCAGGAATACTAAGCAAAGCATAGCCCCAGCAGCAACCGTAATCTCC
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCTATCTTTTACCTCCGCTCGCATACTGCACCACAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAATACATGAACAATGACACACTAACAAACCAACCCACATC
ACAATCGTATTTTAAACCTCTATCTACTATACTTCTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCTAC
CCTTTATCATA-AAAACCTCTAGCATTGTAAACCACCAACCTCCATCTAGCAAAACACC
CACAACTCCAAACACAACCCCTGAACCTGACCATGAACCTAAGCTTTTTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATTCCCAGCCTTA
TTAATCCCTCCCGAGTAAACGTTGAATTACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCTACAATATGA
TTTATCAACCTA-AACAAGACCTACCTCTACTTTAATCTGAGCCACTATTTAATCTT
CTCCTCACCTTAGGACTCATCCAGAAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCTAGAATGAGCTGAATAG
TGGAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTCGGATCCCTACTAGGAATCTGCTTAATCACACAAAT
TGTCACAGGACTATTACTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTCACTTC
TGTCGCCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTCGGCTGACTAATTCGAAACCTCCACGCAAA
TGGAGCCTCCTTTTCTTTATCTGCATCTACTTCCATATCGGCCGAGGATTCTACTACGG
ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAAACCTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTAACACTCATAGC
CACTGCCTTCGTGGGTACGTATTACCTGAGGCAAAATATCATCTGAGGAGTACAGT
AATTACAAACCTATTCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGGCGGATTTCTCAGTAGACAACCCCACTTAACCTCGATTCTTGCCCTCCACTTCTTCT
CCCATTTCATATTGACGGCTCACCCCTAGTGCACCTAACTCTACTACAGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTAGGAATTCATCAGACTGCGACAAAAATCCCATTCACCCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATTCTAGGCTTCGCACCTACTACTAATCTCCTTGCCCTCCCTAGCCCTATT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGACCCAGAAAACCTCACGCCGCAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTATTTCGCTACGCCATCTACGATCTATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTGACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCTAGTCTCTTCCCTCTCCCTTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTCAAACTACGCTCAATAACTTTCCGTCCTCTCACAAATCCTATT
CTGAACCTTAGTAGCCAACCTTCTCGTCTAACTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAACCCAGTCGAACA
CCCA

First records of *Phylloscopus collybita brevirostris* (Strickland, 1837) and *Ph. c. caucasicus* (Loskot, 1991) in north-western Europe

>TT0683CAUC
AAAAATTC TAAGTTACATGCAAGGTCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTGTTGGCCATTTGGACT
GCTTCAGCCCC TAGCAGATGGCGTAAAAC TATTCATCAAAGAACCATCC-ATGAACCCC
CAAGCAAAACTAATCTTACCACCCCATCTCCTAGGAACAGCTATCACAACTCAAGC
AACCACTGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGGCCTTGAATCAACACCCCTCGCTATCCTCCACTA
ATCTCCAAATCCACCATCTCAGCCATCGAAGCCGCAACTAAATAC TTTTTAGTACAA
GCAACTGCCTCTACTTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAACCAACGCATGATATACCGGACAG
TGAGATAATTACCAATTAACCCACCCCATCTCCTGCCTAATTTAACCTCTGCCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTCCATTCCACTTTTGATTTCCCGAAGTCCTCAAGGAGCACCA
CTCACAACCGGGCTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCCCAATCACATTATCTTT
TTAACCTCTCACTCTTTAAACCAACTCTACTA ACTTGATAGCCATTCTCTCTGCTGCT
CTTGGCGGGTGAATAGGACTTAACCCAGCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTTCTTTCT
ATCGCCACCTAGGCTGAATGACCATTATATCTCTTTTGACCCAAAAC TAACTTTACTG
AACTTCTACATCTACAGCCTCATAACTACAGCCACTTTTCTAGCCCTAAACTCAATCAA
GCTTTAAAAC TAACAACCTCATAACAACATGAACAAAAACTCCCTCATTAAACGCAATA
CTAATCTTAACCTACTCTCCCTGGCAGGTCTCCCTCCCTCAGAGGCTTCTGCCAAA
TGATTAATCATTCAGGAATAACTAAGCAAAGCATAGCCCCAGCAGCAACCGTAATCTCC
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCTATCTTTTACCTCGCCTCGCATACTGCACCACAAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAATCACATGAAACAATGACACACTAACAAACCAACCCACATC
ACAATCGCTATTTTAAACCTCTATCTACTATACTTCTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCTAC
CCTTTATCATA-AAAACCTCTAGCATTGTAAACCACCAACCCCTCCATCTAGCAAAACACC
CACAACCTCAAACACAACCCCTGAACCTGACCATGAACCTTAAGCTTTTTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATTCCCAGCCTTA
TTAATCCCTCCCGTAGGTTAACCCTGTAATTAACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCTACAATATGA
TTTATCAACCTA-AACAAGACCTACCTCTACTTTAATCTGAGCCACTATTTAATCTT
CTCCTCACCTTAGGACTCATCCAGAAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCTAGAAATGAGCTGAATAG
TGGAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTCGGATCCCTACTAGGAATCTGCTTAATCACACAAAT
TGTCACAGGACTATTACTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTCACCTC
TGTCGCCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTCGGCTGACTAATTCGAAACCTCCACGCAAA
TGGAGCTCCTTTTCTTTATCTGCATCTACTTCCATATCGGCCGAGGATCTACTACGG
ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAAACCTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTAACACTCATAGC
CACTGCCTTCGTGGGTACGTATTACCTGAGGGCAAAATATCATCTGAGGAGCTACAGT
AATTACAAACCTATTCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGGCGGATTTCTCAGTAGACAACCCACTTAACCTCGATTCTTTCGCCCTCCACTCCTTCT
CCCATTTCATCTGCAAGGCTCACCTTAGTGCACCTAACTCTACTACAGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTAGGAGTTCCATCAGACTGCGACAAAATCCCATTCCACCCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATTTCTAGGCTTCGCACCTATACTAATCCTCCTTGCCTCCCTAGCTCTATT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGACCAGAAAACCTCACGCCGGCAACCCATTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTATTTGCCTACGCCATCTCAGCATCTATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCTCCTAGTCTCTTCCCTCTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTTAAAACCTACGCTCAATAACTTTCCGCCCTCTCACAAAATCCTATT
CTGAACCTTAGTACCAACCTTCTCGTCTA ACTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAAACAGTCGAACA
CCCA

>TT0798MENZ
AAAAATTC TAAGTTACATGCAAGGTCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTGTTGGCCATTTGGACT
GCTTCAACCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAAAC TATTCATCAAAGAGCCATCC-ATGAACCCC
CAAGCAAAACTAATCTTACCACCTAGCCTTATTTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACAACTCAAGC
AACCACTGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGGCCTTGAATCAACACCCCTCGCTATCCTCCACTA
ATCTCCAAATCCACCATCTCCTGAGCCATCGAAGCCGCAACCAAAATAC TTTTTAGTACAA
GCAACTGCCTCTACTTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAACCAACGCATGATATACCGGACAG
TGAGACATTACCAATTAACCCACCCCATCTCCTGCCTAATCTAACCTCTGCCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTTCATTCCACTTTTGATTTCCCGAAGTCCTCAAGGAGCACCA
CTTACAACCCGGCTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCCCAATCACATTATCTTT
TTAACCTCTCACTCTTTAAACCAACTCTACTA ACTTGATAGCCATTCTCTCTGCTGCT
CTTGGCGGGTGAATAGGACTTAACCCAGCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTTCTTTCT
ATCGCCACCTAGGCTGAATGACCATTATATCTCTTTTGACCCAAAAC TAACTTTACTG
AACTTCTACATCTACAGCTCATAACTGCAGCCACTTTTCTAGCCCTAAACTCAATCAA
GCTTTAAAAC TAACAACCTCATAACAACATGAACAAAAACTCCCTCATTAAACGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCCTAGCAGGTCTCCCTCCCTCAGAGGCTTCTGCCAAA
TGATTGATCATTAAGAATAACTAAGCAAAGCATAGCCCCAGCAGCAACCGTAATCTCC
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCTATTCTTTTACCTCGCCTCGCATACTGCACCACAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAATCACATGAAACAATGACACACTAACAAACCAACCCACATC
ACAATCGCCATTTTAAACCTCTATCTACTATACTTCTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCTAC
CCTTTATCATA-AAAACCTCTAACATTTGTAAACCACCAACCCCTCCATCTAGCAAAACACC
CACAACCTCAAACACAACCCCTGAACCTGACCATGAACCTTAAGCTTCTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATTCCCAGCCTTA
TTAATCCCTCCCGAGTTAACCCTGTAATTAACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCTACAATATGA
TTTATCAATCTA-AACAAGACCTACCTCTACTTTAATCTGAGCCACTATTTAATCTT
CTCCTCACCTTAGGACTTATCCAGAAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCTAGAAATGAGCTGAATAG
TAGAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTCGGATCCCTATTAGGAATCTGCTTAATCACACAAAT
TGTCACAGGACTATTACTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTCACCTC
TGTCGCTCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTCGGCTGACTAATTCGAAACCTCCACGCAAA
CGGAGCCTCCTTTTCTTTATCTGCATCTACTTCCATATCGGCCGAGGATCTACTACGG
ATCGTACCTAAACAAAGAAACCTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTAACACTCATAGC
CACTGCCTTCGTGGGATACGTATTACCTGAGGGCAAAATATCATCTGAGGAGCCACAGT
AATTACAAACCTATTCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG

First records of *Phylloscopus collybita brevirostris* (Strickland, 1837) and *Ph. c. caucasicus* (Loskot, 1991) in north-western Europe

AGGCGGATTCTCAGTAGACAACCCCACTCTAACTCGATTCTTCGCCCTCCACTTCCTTCT
CCCATTTCATCATGTCAGGGCTCACCCCTAGTGCACCTAACGCTACTACAGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTTAGGAATTCATCAGACTGCGCAAAAATCCCATTCACCCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATCTCAGGCTTCGCACACTATACTAATCCTCCTTCGCCCTAGCCCTATT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGACCCAGAAAACCTCAGCGCGCCAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTATTGCTTACGCCATCCTACGATCTATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTGACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCTAGTCTCTTCCCTCCTTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTCAAACTACGCTCAATAAATTTCCGTCCCTCTCACAAAATCCTATT
CTGAACCCCTAGTAGCCAACCTTCTCGTCTAATTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAACCAGTCGAACA
CCCA

>TT0056MENZ

AAAAATCTAAGTTACATGCAAGGTCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTGTTGGCCATTGGACT
GCTTCAACCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAAACCTATTCATCAAAGAGCCCATCC-ATGAACCC
CAAGCAAACCTAATCTTACCATCAGCCTTATTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACAACTCAAGC
AACCACTGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGGCCTTGAATCAACACCCCTCGCTATCCTCCACTA
ATCTCCAAATCCCACTCCTCAGGCTCAGCCATCGAAGCCGCAACCAAACTATTTTGTACAA
GCAACTGCCTCTACCTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAACCAACGCATGATATACCGGACAG
TGAGACATTACCAATTAACCCACCCCATCTCCTGCTTAACTTAACTTCCGCTTGCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTTCATTCACCTTTTGATTTCCCGAAGTCTTCAAGGAGCACCA
CTTACAACCGGGCTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCAATCACATTATCTTT
TTAACCTCTACTCTTTAAACCAACTCTACTAATTTGCATAGCCATTCTCTGCTGCT
CTTGGCGGGTGAATAGGACTTAAACCAGACCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTCTCTTCT
ATCGCCACCTAGGCTGAATGACCATTATATCTCTTTTGACCCAAAACCTAACCTTACTG
AACTTCTACATCTACAGCCTCATAAATGCAGCCACTTTTCTAGCCCTAACTCAATCAA
GCTTTAAAACCTAACACCCCTCATAACAACATGAACAAAACTCCCTCATTAACGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCCTAGCAGTCTCCTCCCTCAGAGGCTTCTGCCCCAAA
TGATTAATCATTAAGAATAAAGCAAGCATAGCCCCAGCAGCAACCGTAACTCTCC
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCTTATTCTTTTACCTCGCCTCGCATACTGCACCACAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAAATCACATGAAACAATGACACACTAACAAACCAACCCACATC
ACAATCGCCATTTTAAACCACTCTATCTACTATACTTCTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCTAC
CCTTTATCATA-AAAACCTCTAACATTTGTAACCACCAACCCCTCCATCTAGCAAAAACACC
CACAACTCCAAACACAACCCCTGAACCTGACCATGAACCTAAGCTTCTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATTTCCAGCCTTA
TTAATCCCTCCCGAGTAAACGTTGAATTACAGCCGCTCTCCACCTACAATTATGA
TTTATCAATCTA-AACAGACCTTACCTTACTTTAATCTGAGCCACTATTTTAACTCT
CTCCTCACCCCTAGGCTTATCCAGCAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCTAGAATGGGCTGAATAG
TAGAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTCGGATCCCTATTAGGAATCTGCTTAACTCACACAAAT
TGTCACAGGACTATTACTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTCACTTC
TGTCGCTCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTCGGCTGACTAATTCGAAACCTCCAGCAAA
CGGAGCCTCCTTTTTCTTTATCTGCATCTACTTCCATATCGGCCGAGGATTCTACTACGG
ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAACTTGAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTTAACTCATAGC
CACTGCCTTCGTCGGATACGTATTACCCTGAGGGCAAAATATCATCTGAGGAGCCACAGT
AATTACAAACCTATTCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGGCGGATTCTCAGTAGACAACCCCACTCTAACTCGATTCTTCGCCCTCCACTTCCTTCT
CCCATTTCATCTTTCAGGGCTCACCCCTAGTGCACCTAACGCTACTACAGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTAGGAATTCATCAGACTGCGCAAAAATCCCATTCACCCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATTTCTAGGCTTCGCACCTATACTAATCCTCCTTGCCCTCCTAGCCCTATT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGACCCAGAAAACCTCAGCGCGCCAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTTATTTGCTTACGCCATCCTACGATCTATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTGACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCTAGTCTCTTCCCTCCTTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTCAAACTACGCTCAATAAATTTCCGTCCCTCTCACAAAATCCTATT
CTGAACCCCTAGTAGCCAACCTTCTCGTCTAATTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAACCAGTCGAACA
CCCA

>TT0057MENZ

AAAAATCTAAGTTACATGCAAGGTCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTGTTGGCCATTGGACT
GCTTCAACCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAAACCTATTCATCAAAGAGCCCATCC-ATGAACCC
CAAGCAAACCTAATCTTACCATCAGCCTTATTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACAACTCAAGC
AACCACTGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGGCCTTGAATCAACACCCCTCGCTATCCTCCACTA
ATCTCCAAATCCCACTCCTCAGGCTCAGCCATCGAAGCCGCAACCAAACTATTTTGTACAA
GCAACTGCCTCTACCTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAACCAACGCATGATATACCGGACAG
TGAGACATTACCCAATTAACCCCACTCCTCCTGCTTAACTTAACTTCCGCTTGCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTTCATTCACCTTTTGATTTCCCGAAGTCTTCAAGGAGCACCA
CTTACAACCGGGCTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCAATCACATTATCTTT
TTAACCTCTACTCTTTAAACCAACTCTACTAATTTGCATAGCCATTCTCTGCTGCT
CTTGGCGGGTGAATAGGCTTAAACCAGACCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTCTCTTCT
ATCGCCACCTAGGCTGAATGACCATTATATCTCTTTTGACCCAAAACCTAACCTTACTG
AACTTCTACATCTACAGCCTCATAAATGCAGCCACTTTTCTAGCCCTAACTCAATCAA
GCTTTAAAACCTAACACCCCTCATAACAACATGAACAAAACTCCCTCATTAACGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCTTAGCAGGTCTCCTCCCTCAGAGGCTTCTGCCCCAAA
TGATTAATCATTAAGAATAAAGCAAGCATAGCCCCAGCAGCAACCGTAACTCTCC
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCTTATTCTTTTACCTCGCCTCGCATACTGCACCACAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAAATCACATGAAACAATGACACACTAACAAACCAACCCACATC
ACAATCGCCATTTTAAACCTCTATCTACTATACTTCTACTATCTCCCTTTAATCTAC
CCTTTATCATA-AAAACCTCTAACATTTGTAACCACCAACCCCTCCATCTAGCAAAAACACC
CACAACTCCAAACACAACCCCTGAACCTGACCATGAACCTAAGCTTCTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATTTCCAGCCTTA

First records of *Phylloscopus collybita brevirostris* (Strickland, 1837) and *Ph. c. caucasicus* (Loskot, 1991) in north-western Europe

TTAATCCCCTCCCAGGTAACCGTTGAATTACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCCTACAATTATGA
TTTATCAATCTA-AACAAGACCCCTACCTCTACTTTAATCTGAGCCACTATTTTAAATTCCT
CTCCTCACCCCTAGGACTTATCCACGAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCCTAGAATGGGCTGAATAG
TAGAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTCGGATCCCTATTAGGAATCTGCTTAATCACACAAAT
TGTCACAGGACTATTACTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTCACTTC
TGTCGCTCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTCGGCTGACTAATTCGAAACCTCCACGCAA
CGGAGCCTCCTTTTCTTATCTGCATCTACTTCCATATCGGGCCGAGGATTCTACTACGG
ATCGTACCTAAACAAAGAACTTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTAAACACTCATAGC
CACTGCCTTCGTCGGATACGTATTACCCTGAGGGCAAATATCATTCTGAGGAGCCACAGT
AATTACAAACCTATTCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGGCGGATTCTCAGTAGACAACCCCACTCTAATTCGATTCTTCGCCCTCCACTTCCTTCT
CCCATTTCATATGACAGGCTCACCCCTAGTGCACCTAACGCTACTACACGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTAGGAATTCCATCAGACTGCGACAAAATCCCATTCCACCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATCTAGGCTTCGCCTCATACTAATCTCCTTGCCCTCCCTAGCCCTATT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGACCCAGAAAACCTCACGCCGGCCAAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTATTTCGCTACGCCATCCCTAGATCTATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTGACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCTAGTCTCTTCCCTCTTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTCAAACCTAGCTCAATAACTTTCCGTCGCCCTCTCACAAATCCTATT
CTGAACCCCTAGTAGCCAACTTCTCGTCTAATTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAACCAGTCGAACA
CCCA

>TT1113HERM

AAAAATTCTAAGTTACATGCAAGGTCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTGTTGGCCATTGGACT
GCTTCAACCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAAACCTATTCATCAAAGAACCCTCC-ATGAACCC
CAAGCAAACCTAATCTTACCCTCAGCCTTCTTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACAACTCAAGC
AACCACTGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGGCCTTGAAATCAACACCCCTCGCTATCCTCCACTA
ATCTCCAAATCCACCATCCCGGAGCCATCGAAGCCGCAACCAATACCTTTTGTAGTACAA
GCAACTGCCTCTACTTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAACCAACGCATGATATACCGGACAG
TGAGATATTACCAATTAACCCACCCCACTCTCCTGCCTAATCTAACCTCTGCCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTCCCATTCCACTTTTGATTTCCCGAAGTCCTTCAAGGAGCACCA
CTCACAACCGGGCTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCCCAATCACATTATTCTTT
TTAACCTCTCACTCTTTAAACCCAACTCTACTAATTTGCATAGCCATTCTCTCCGCTGCT
CTTGGCGGGTGGATAGGACTTAACCCAGCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTCTCTTCT
ATCGCCACCTAGGCTGAATGACCATTATATCTCTTTTGACCCAAAACCTAACCTTACTG
AACTTCTACATCTACAGCCTCATAACTGCAGCCACTTTTCTAGCCCTAAACTCAATCAA
GCTTTAAAACCTAACACCCCTCATAAACACATGAACAAAACCTCCCTCATTAACCGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCTAGCAGTCTCCTCCCTCACAGGCTTCTCTACTCTAA
TGATTAATCATTTCAAGAGCTAACTAAGCAAAGCATAGCCCCAGCAGCAACCGTAATCTCC
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCTATTCTTTTACCTCGCCTCGCATACTGCACCACAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACCACAAATCACATGAAACAAATGACACACTAACAAACCAACCCACATC
ACAATCGCCATTTTAAACCTCTATCTACTATACTTCTACTATCTCCCTTTAATCCAC
CCTTTATCTTA-AAAACCTCCTAGCATTGTAACCACCAACCCCTCCATCTAGCAAGACCC
CACAACCTCAAACACAACCCCTGAACCTGACCATGAACCTAAGCTTCTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCTCCTCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATTTCCAGCCCTTA
TTAATCCCTCCCGGTAACCGCTGAATCACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCCCTACAATTGTGA
TTTATCAATCTA-AACAAGACCCCTACCTCTACTTTAATCTGAGCCACTTCTAATTTTC
CTCCTCACCTAGGACTTATCCAGCAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCCTAGAATGAGCTGAATAG
TAGAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTTGGATCCCTATTAGGAATCTGCTTAATCACACAAAT
TGTCACAGGACTATTACTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTCACTTC
TGTCGCCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTCGGCTGACTAATTCGAAACCTCCACGCAA
CGGAGCCTCCTTTTCTTATCTGCATCTACTTCCATATCGGGCCGAGGATTCTACTACGG
ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAACTTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTAAACACTCATAGC
CACTGCCTTCGTCGGGTACGTATTACCCTGAGGACAAAATATCATTTCTGAGGAGCCACAGT
AATTACAAACCTATTCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGGCGGATTCTCAGTAGACAACCCCACTCTAATTCGATTCTTCGCCCTCCACTTCCTTAT
CCCATTCAATATGACAGGCTCACACTAGTGCACCTAACCCCTACTACACGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTAGGAATTCCATCAGACTGCGACAAAATCCCATTCCACCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATCTAGGTTTCGCACCTACATACTAATCTCCTTGCCCTCCCTAGCCCTATT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGACCCAGAAAACCTCACGCCAGCCAAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTATTTCGCTACGCCATCCCTAGGATCCATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTGACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCTAGTCTCTTCCCTCTTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTCAAACCTAGCTCAATAACTTTCCGTCGCCCTCTCACAAATCCTTAT
CTGAACCCCTAGTAGCCAACTTCTCGTCTAATTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAACCAGTCGAACA
CCCA

>TT1114HERM

AAAAATTCTAAGTTACATGCAAGGTCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTGTTGGCCATTGGACT
GCTTCAACCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAAACCTATTCATCAAAGAACCCTCC-ATGAACCC
CAAGCAAACCTAATCTTACCCTCAGCCTTCTTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACAACTCAAGC
AACCACTGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGGCCTTGAAATCAACACCCCTCGCTATCCTCCACTA
ATCTCCAAATCCACCCCTTCCAGCCATCGAAGCCGCAACCAATACCTTTTGTAGTACAA
GCAACTGCCTCTACTTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAACCAACGCATGATATACCGGACAG
TGAGATATTACCAATTAACCCACCCCACTCTCCTGCCTAATCTAACCTCTGCCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTCCCATTCCACTTTTGATTTCCCGAAGTCCTTCAAGGAGCACCA
CTCACAACCGGGCTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCCCAATCACATTATTCTTT
TTAACCTCTCACTCTTTAAACCCAACTCTACTAATTTGCATAGCCATTCTCTCCGCTGCT
CTTGGCGGGTGGATAGGACTTAACCCAGCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTCTCTTCT
ATCGCCACCTAGGCTGAATGACCATTATATCTCTTTTGACCCAAAACCTAACCTTACTG

First records of *Phylloscopus collybita brevirostris* (Strickland, 1837) and *Ph. c. caucasicus* (Loskot, 1991) in north-western Europe

AACTTCTACATCTACAGCCTCATAACTGCAGCCACTTTTCTAGCCCTAAACTCAATCAAA
GCTTTAAACTAACAACCTCATAACAACATGAACAAAACTCCCTCATTAACCGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCCTAGCAGGTCTCCCTCCCTCAGAGGCTTCCCTACCCAAA
TGATTAATCATCAAGAGCTAACTAAGCAAAGCATAGCCCCAGCAGCAACCGTAATCTCC
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCCTATTCTTTTACCTCCGCTCGCATACTGCACCACAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAATACATGAACAATGACACACTAACAAACCAACCCACATC
ACAATCGCCATTTAACCCTCTATCTACTATACTTCTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCCAC
CCTTTATCCTA-AAAACCTCCTAGCATTGTAAACCACCAACCTCCATCTAGCAAGACACC
CACAACCTCAAACACAACCCCTGAACTGACCATGAACCTAAGCTTCTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATCCCGAGCCTTA
TTAATCCCTCCCGAGGTAACCGCTGAATCACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCTACAATTGTGA
TTTATCAATCTA-AACAAGACCTACCTCTACTTAACTCTGAGCCACTATTCTAATTTTC
CTCCTCACCTTAGGACTTATCCACGAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCTAGAATGAGCTGAATAG
TAGAAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTTGGATCCCTATTAGGAATCTGCTTAATCACACAAAT
TGTCACAGGACTATTACTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTCACTTC
TGTCGCCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTTCGGCTGACTAATTTCGAAACCTCCACGCAA
CGGAGCCTCCTTTTCTTATCTGCATCTACTTCCATATCGGCCGAGGATTCTACTACGG
ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAACTTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTAAACATCATAGC
CACTGCCTTCGTCGGGTACGTATTACCCTGAGGACAAATATCATTTCTGAGGAGCCACAGT
AATTACAAACCTATTCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGGCGGATTCTCAGTAGACAACCCCACTCTAACTCGATTCTTCGCCCTCCACTTCCTTCT
CCCATTCATTATGTCAGGGCTCACCTTAGTGCACCTAACTCTACTACAGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTAGGAATTCATCAGACTGCGCAAAAATCCCATTCACCCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATTTCTAGTTTTCGCACCTACATAATCCCTCCTTGCCCTCCCTAGCCCTAT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGACCCAGAAAACTTCACGCCAGCCAAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTTATTTCGCTACGCCATCCTACGATCCATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTGACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCCTAGTCTCTTCCCTCCTTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTCAAACCTAGCTCAATAACTTTCCGTCCTCCTCACAAATCTTAT
CTGAACCTTAGTAGCCAACTTCTCGTCTAACTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAAACAGTCGAACA
CCCA

>TT1117HERM

AAAAATTCTAAGTTACATGCAAGGTCGAAAAGGCCAAACATTGTTGGCCATTGGACT
GCTTCAACCCCTAGCAGATGGCGTAAAACCTATTCATCAAGAACCCATCC-ATGAACCC
CAGCAAAACTAATCTTACCATCAGCCTTCTTCTAGGAACAGCTATCACAACCTCAAGC
AACCCTGAATCATAGCCTGAGCCGGCCTTGAAATCAACACCCCTCGCTATCCTCCCACTA
ATCTCCAAATCCACCCTCAGGAGCCTCAGGAGCCATCGAAGCCGCAACCAAACTTTTGTACAA
GCAACTGCCTCTACTTTACTACTATTCTCCAGCATAACCAACGCATGATATACCGGACAG
TGAGATATTACCAATTAACCCACCCCATCTCCTGCCTAATCTAACCTCTGCATTGCA
ATAAACTAGGACTAGTCCCATTTCCACTTTTGATTTCCCGAAGTCTTCAAGGAGCACA
CTCACAACCCGGCTACTTCTAGCCACAGTCATGAAATTTCCCAATCACATTTCTTT
TTAACCTCTCACTTTTAAACCCCACTACTACTAACTTGATAGCCATTCTCCTCGCTGCT
CTTGGCGGGTGGATAGGACTTAAACCAGACCCAGATCCGAAAAATCCTAGCTTTCTTCT
ATCGCCACCTTAGGCTGAATGACCATTATTTATCTCTTTTGACCCAAAACCTAACTTTACTG
AACTTCTACATCTACAGCCTCATAACTGCAGCCACTTTTCTAGCCCTAAACTCAATCAAA
GCTTTAAAACCTAACCCCTCATAACAACATGAACAAAACTCCCTCATTAACCGCAATA
CTATTCTTAACCTACTCTCCCTAGCAGGTCTCCCTCCCTCAGAGGCTTCTTACCCAAA
TGATTAATCATCAAGAGCTAACTAAGCAAAGCATAGCCCCAGCAGCAACCGTAATCTCC
CTTTTATCCCTACTAGGCCTATTCTTTTACCTCCGCTCGCATACTGCACCACAATCACA
TTACCTCCACACACCACAATACATGAAACAATGACACACTAACAAACCAACCCACATC
ACAATCGCCATTTAACCCTCTATCTACTATACTTCTACCTATCTCCCTTTAATCCAC
CCTTTATCCTA-AAAACCTTAGCATTGTAAACCACCAACCTCCATCTAGCAAGACACC
CACAACCTCAAACACAACCCCTGAACTGACCATGAACCTAAGCTTCTTCGACCAATTC
TCAAGCCCTCCCTCCTAGGAATTCATTAATCCTCATCGCAACAGCATCCCGAGCCTTA
TTAATCCCTCCCGAGGTAACCGCTGAATCACAAGCCGCTCTCCACCTACAATTGTGA
TTTATCAATCTA-AACAAGACCTACCTCTACTTAACTCTGAGCCACTATTCTAATTTTC
CTCCTCACCTTAGGACTTATCCACGAATGAGCCCAAGGAGGCTAGAATGAGCTGAATAG
TAGAAAAGTTAGTCTAACT-AACTTTGGATCCCTATTAGGAATCTGCTTAATCACACAAAT
TGTCACAGGACTATTACTAGCCATACACTACACAGCAGACACATCCCTAGCATTCACTTC
TGTCGCCACACATGCCGAAACGTTCAATTTCGGCTGACTAATTTCGAAACCTCCACGCAA
CGGAGCCTCCTTTTCTTATCTGCATCTACTTCCATATCGGCCGAGGATTCTACTACGG
ATCGTATCTAAACAAAGAACTTGAAACATCGGAGTTATCCTACTATTAACTCATAGC
CACTGCCTTCGTCGGGTACGTATTACCCTGAGGACAAATATCATTTCTGAGGAGCCACAGT
AATTACAAACCTATTCTCAGCAATCCCATACATTTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCATG
AGGCGGATTCTCAGTAGACAACCCCACTCTAACTCGATTCTTCGCCCTCCACTTCCTTCT
CCCATTCATTATGTCAGGGCTCACCTTAGTGCACCTAACTCTACTACAGAAACAGGATC
AAACAACCCCTAGGAATTCATCAGACTGCGCAAAAATCCCATTCACCCCTACTACTC
TACAAAAGACATTTCTAGTTTTCGCACCTACATAATCCCTCCTTGCCCTCCCTAGCCCTAT
CTCACCTAACCTACTAGGAGACCCAGAAAACTTCACGCCAGCCAAACCCACTAGCCACACC
CCCTCACATTAACCCGAATGATATTTCTTATTTCGCTACGCCATCCTACGATCCATCCC
AAACAACCTAGGAGGTGACTAGCCCTAGCCGCTCAGTCCTAGTCTCTTCCCTCCTTCC
CCTCCTCCACACTTCAAACCTAGCTCAATAACTTTCCGTCCTCCTCACAAATCTTAT
CTGAACCTTAGTAGCCAACTTCTCGTCTAACTTGAGTAGGAAGCCAAACAGTCGAACA
CCCA